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Authors' contributions

Per CRediT taxonomy – MM:

Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing; HP: Investigation, Resources, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing; LSM: Literature review, database analysis and website search; EMF:

Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing; SYS: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing; TK: Formal Analysis, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing; *Additional ICMJE criteria:* All authors approved this version to be published, agreed to be accountable for their contributions, and agreed to address any questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work, including of part they were not personally involved in.

Original Article

Peer review types in European Association of Science Editors members' journals: a survey study

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Code availability

Statistical analysis outputs and code are available at Stanford Digital Repository (<https://doi.org/10.25740/bd297js0259>).

Data availability

The raw and cleaned dataset is posted at Stanford Digital Repository (<https://doi.org/10.25740/bd297js0259>).

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Funder's role

MM is the chair of the EASE Peer Review Committee, and his role is described above.

Presentations at meetings/conferences

None.

Preprint availability

This is the first version of the study.

Protocol and analysis plan availability

The study did not have a published protocol with the analysis plan.

Reporting

This study was designed and reported following the Strengthening of the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines and the Consensus Based Checklist for Reporting of Survey Studies (CROSS).

Competing interests

Mario Malički is EASE Peer Review Committee Chair and a member of the International Advisory Board of European Science Editing; and all co-authors are members of EASE.

Abstract

Introduction: The number or percentage of journals publishing review reports or reviewer names remains unknown in today's scholarly milieu.

Methods: In January 2025 we sent a survey to all members of the European Association of Science Editors (EASE), followed by 2 reminder rounds, with 16 questions related to their journals, including type of peer review, availability of post-publication commenting, journal discipline, articles access type, and the manuscript submission system used by the journal. Survey responses were verified by checking the information listed on the journals' websites.

Results: A total of 84 participants completed the survey out of the 668 emails sent (of which 83 bounced, and 125 were unopened), leading to a response rate of 14% (84 out of 585 working or non-bounced emails), or 18% (84 out of 460) if only opened emails are counted. After data cleaning, information on 71 unique journals was collected, of which only 2 described their peer review type using the National Information Standards Organization (NISO) 2023 peer review taxonomy. Of the 71 journals, one published review reports with reviewer names and one without. Four journals allowed post-publication commenting on their websites. A little over a third of the journals used the Open Journal System (n = 22, or 31%) as their submission platform, were health sciences journals (n = 23, or 32%), were published by institutional publishers (n = 25, 35%), and more than half operated as Diamond open access (n = 42, 59%).

Discussion: Only two journals in our survey published review reports alongside articles, and of the two, one published reviewer names (used open peer review) and one did not (transparent peer review). Additionally, only two journals described their peer review process on their websites using the NISO taxonomy. More research is needed to determine barriers and interventions for greater adoption of open and transparent peer review and the NISO taxonomy.

Keywords:

Editors, journals, peer review, survey

Introduction

In 2017, a systematic review reported 22 different definitions of the term 'open peer review'.¹ In July 2023, new peer review terminology was published as a National Information Standards Organization (NISO) standard.² National Information Standards Organization is a non-profit organization accredited by the American National Standards Institute that focuses on developing and maintaining technical standards and recommended practices for managing information in the changing digital landscape. According to that standard (which journals can opt to follow), journal peer review should be explained in relation to the four elements of the peer review process: (1) identity transparency (between the editor, reviewers, and authors), (2) who the reviewer(s) interact with, (3) what information about the review process is published, and (4) whether and how post-publication commenting happens. Although the standard does not use the term open peer review, the present study defined **open peer review** as a type of peer review in which review reports and the reviewer identities are published alongside the article (example: *RIPR journal*³) and **transparent peer review** as a type of peer review in which review reports are published alongside the article, but the identity of the reviewers is not revealed (example: *BMC Medicine*⁴). Additionally, the study defined **opt-in peer review** as a type of peer review in which journals allow reviewers to choose between open and transparent peer review (example: *PLOS ONE*⁵).

Earlier studies have shown a steady growth in open peer review since 2001, with 38 publishers and 617 journals in 2019 using some form of open, transparent, or opt-in peer review.⁶ In January 2025, among 2033 journals published by Wiley, only one

journal (0.05%), namely the *European Journal of Immunology*, was listed as using opt-in peer review; two journals (0.1%), namely the *Asian Economic Policy Review* and the *European Journal of Neuroscience*, were listed as using open peer review; and 17 (0.8%) were listed as using transparent peer review.⁷ In the same year, Brieflands used the opt-in model for all the 58 journals it published,⁸ whereas of 1382 journals published by Sage, 9 (0.7%) were listed as using transparent peer review.⁹ Of 298 BMC journals, 21 (7%) were listed as using open peer review and 40 (13%), as using transparent peer review. In July 2024, of 20,649 indexed journals in the DOAJ database, only one (*BMC Digital Health*) used transparent peer review and 276 (1%) journals used open peer review. The movement toward more open and transparent peer review is actively developing as funders, institutions, and researchers advocate for increased transparency in the research process.

The primary goal of this study was to determine the number and the proportion of peer-reviewed journals that used open, transparent, or opt-in peer review – and whose members are part of EASE.

Methods

Study design

The present study was a cross-sectional survey-based study that was part of the EASE Transparency in Peer Review Project.¹⁰ In January 2024, the EASE Peer Review Committee, chaired by Mario Malički, posted a call for collaborators on this project to all EASE members using the EASE forum and the EASE newsletter, and accepted all applicants to help with specific aspects of the study (their roles are described using the CRediT taxonomy).

Data collection and participants

After initial development by the authors, the survey was sent to a panel of experts for content validation (that is, for checking if the questions addressed the aims of the study) and then the same version was sent for testing to several journal editors for additional testing and feedback (both groups are listed in the acknowledgements). Both processes occurred from September to December 2024. The final version consisted of 16 questions (5 mandatory and 11 optional) and covered information about the participant's journal, its peer review type(s), discipline, business model, and the manuscript submission system. Full survey questions are listed in the Supplement 1.

Participants

All registered EASE members were invited to participate in the survey.

Survey administration

On 15 January 2025, the survey was sent, using the SurveyMonkey platform, to all EASE members. Reminders were sent to those who failed to respond, one on 29 January and one on 11 February. The survey was closed on 1 March.

Data cleaning and preparation

Collected data were cleaned and validated to ensure accuracy and consistency. Duplicated records were checked manually, and in case of multiple submissions of conflicting information about the same journal, the data were checked using the journal's website. For the following aspects, two authors (MM and TK) also checked how and whether those aspects were described on the journals' pages (in terms of the categories used in the survey):

- use of the 2023 NISO Terminology
- publicly available instructions or guidelines for reviewers

- type of peer review
- journal's practice regarding editors' comments
- journal's practice regarding author responses and rebuttal letters
- interaction type that occurs between the editor, authors, and reviewers
- whether and who can post online comments on articles on the journal's website.

'Other' categories of responses for each question were re-coded (when possible) into existing categories or classified into new ones and saved as part of the cleaned data set. We shared both the cleaned and the verified data set in our project repository (<https://doi.org/10.25740/bd297js0259>).

Mapping

A geospatial approach was used to show the geographical distribution of the collected data. The mapping was done in ESRI ArcGIS ver. 10.6.1 by filling in the total number of journals per country in the attribute table of the shapefile. The final visualization (Figure 1) contains two map frames, namely an overview of the world and a detailed map of the European continent, in which colours represent the total number of journals reported, by country.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were calculated for each survey question. A summary of the total number of responses, completed surveys, and the distribution of mandatory and optional questions was provided. The overall response rate and response rates for each question were presented. Statistical environment R ver. 4.4 was used for statistical analysis, and the statistical output was deposited in our project repository to demonstrate computational reproducibility.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of journals participating in the survey.

Ethics approval

This research was exempt from the need for an institutional ethics board review, as no personal information was collected and the research posed no risk to participants.

Results

Of 668 emails sent, 83 bounced, and 125 were unopened. A total of 84 participants completed the survey, leading to a response rate of 14% (84 out of 585 working, that is non-bounced, emails), or 18% (84 out of 460) if only opened emails were counted. During data cleaning, four duplicate entries (regarding the same journal) and eight incomplete answers were removed. Finally, one entry regarding a journal without peer review was excluded from further analysis. In total, the participants reported characteristics of 71 unique peer-reviewed journals (Tables 1 and 2). The journal names, website links, and the ISSNs are reported in our raw data.

Of 71 unique journals, only 2 used the 2023 NISO Terminology and 41 (58%) had publicly available guidelines for peer reviewers. In 3 journals, authors could choose the type of

peer review, namely between either single- or double-anonymized peer review, between double-anonymized or published peer review, and between double-anonymized or 'crowd' review. Among the remaining journals, two thirds of journals (47, or 66%) used double-anonymized review, 17 (24%) used single-anonymized review, 2 used unpublished peer reviews with opt-in identity reveal, 1 (*Research Integrity and Peer Review*) used open peer review, and 1 (*Health Research Policy and Systems*) used published peer reviews with opt-in identity reveal. Almost two thirds of journals (43, or 61%; Table 2) had been using the same peer review type for more than 10 years.

All journals (71, 100%) had 'Author-Editor' as the dominant interaction type (that is, per NISO taxonomy, authors communicate directly only with the editor), and one journal allowed communication between reviewers. The editor's comments were published by one journal, and two published authors' responses (rebuttals). Only four journals allowed post-publication comments about the articles on their websites.

The year when a journal was founded was available for 67 journals, of which 35 (52%)

Table 1. Characteristics and peer review types of EASE member journals

Answer	Reported by respondents		Information on the journals' website	
	n	%	n	%
The peer review process is described on the journal's website using the 2023 NISO Terminology (N=71)				
Yes	36	51	2	3
No	15	21	69	97
Unsure/Don't know	20	28	0	0
Instructions/guidelines for reviewers are publicly available (N=71)				
Yes	46	65	41	58
No	23	32	30	42
Unsure/Don't know	2	3	0	0
The type of peer review, employed by journal ^a (N=71)				
Single anonymized	16	23	17	24
Double anonymized	45	63	47	66
Triple anonymized	1	1	0	0
Unpublished, with opt-in identity reveal	1	1	2	3
Open	3	4	1	1
Transparent	0	0	0	0
Published with opt-in identity reveal	0	0	1	1
Single anonymized with opt-in identity reveal for reviewers	2	3	0	0
Authors chose double anonymized or published peer review reports (with reviewers able to choose whether to sign their names)	1	1	1	1
Authors choose single- or double-anonymized	1	1	1	1
Authors choose double anonymized or 'Crowd review'	1	1	1	1
A journal's dominant practice regarding editors' comments (responded: N=70; validated: N=71)				
All editor(s)' comments published alongside the review reports	8	11	1	1
Editor(s)' comments not published	61	87	69	97
Other ('Sometimes editor's comment is published')	1	1	1	1
Not responded	1	1	0	0
A journal's dominant practice regarding author responses / rebuttal letters (N=71)				
All author responses and rebuttal letters published	5	7	2	3
Only author responses and rebuttal letters of those authors that opt-in published	3	4	1	1
Author responses and rebuttal letters not published	63	89	68	96
Other	0	0	0	0
The dominant interaction type that occurs between the editor, authors, and reviewers ^a (N=71) ^a				
Author(s) communicate directly only with decision-making editor	68	96	70	99
Author(s) communicate or collaborate directly with reviewer(s)	0	0	0	0
Reviewers communicate with one another	0	0	0	0
Author(s) communicate directly only with decision-making editor; author(s) communicate or collaborate directly with reviewer(s)	1	1	0	0
Author(s) communicate directly only with decision-making editor; reviewers communicate with one another	0	0	1 ^b	1
Other (in the past, rare cases of author also allowed to communicate with reviewers along with author–editor interaction)	2	3	0	0

Continued

Table 1. Characteristics and peer review types of EASE member journals (Continued)

Answer	Reported by respondents		Information on the journals' website	
	n	%	n	%
A journal allows online comments to articles on website (N=71)				
Commenting available to anybody. Can be anonymous, require signing in and/or registration (for example, via ORCID)	6	8	4	6
Commenting available by invitation only, that is only those individuals invited or approved by editor (or publisher) can comment on the review on the journal's website	2	3	0	0
Commenting not possible on journal's website	61	86	67	94
Other (publishing Letters to Editor; commenting on LinkedIn, etc.)	2	3	0	0

EASE, European Association of Science Editors.

^amultiple answers allowed ^bjournal uses author–editor communication as main type of interaction and offers reviewer–reviewer interaction for 20%–25% of eligible manuscripts ('crowd' review)

were founded since 1996, with about a quarter (18, or 27%) founded between 2000 and 2020. Almost a third of journals (23, or 32%) were health sciences journals, published by institutional publishers (25, or 35%), under Diamond open access (42, or 59%), and used Open Journal System (22, or 31%) as their manuscript submission platform. Most journal publishers were based in Europe and Asia (Figure 1).

Discussion

In our survey of the 71 unique journals, about a third of journals were health sciences journals, published by institutional publishers, and the majority were published as Diamond open access. Overall, these journals had a low uptake of open and transparent peer review. Only two journals published review reports: one published the reports with the names of the reviewers and the other without. Three journals allowed authors to choose between different peer review types. These findings are in alignment with earlier research, which showed less than 1% of all scholarly journals used any type of open, transparent, or opt-in peer review.^{6–11} We found a discrepancy between the respondents' answers about

the journals and the information listed on the journals' websites. The widest discrepancy was related to the use of the new NISO 2023 taxonomy to describe the peer review process. Specifically, 36 (51%) of the journals used the new NISO taxonomy – going by the responses; however, going by the information on the websites, the taxonomy was used by only two journals. This difference is probably due to the respondents being unfamiliar with the new NISO taxonomy. This is not surprising because even large publishers, with many support staff, are yet to update their journals' websites to align with the new taxonomy. The International Association of Scientific, Technical, and Medical Publishers (STM) new dashboard showed, in September 2025, that only one publisher – IOP Publishing – had aligned all its journals with the taxonomy; no information about other publishers is available at this point.¹¹ We are aware that the taxonomy is not mandatory and that it has limitations: for example, it does not allow easy classification of types of peer review or an extra category for journals that allow reviewers to choose between different peer review types. Furthermore, current metadata standards in large bibliographic databases do not have peer review type as a characteristic of journals, although

Table 2. Peer review type, duration, journal discipline, publisher type, and journal submission system used by participating journals

Item in the survey	Reported by respondents	
	n	%
Peer review type duration (N = 71)		
0 to 4 years	5	7
5 to 9 years	20	28
10 or more years	43	61
Not known or not sure	3	4
Journal main discipline (N = 71)		
Arts and humanities	10	14
Health sciences	23	32
Life sciences	10	14
Physical sciences	1	1
Social sciences	18	25
Multidisciplinary	9	13
Publisher type (N = 71)		
Institutional	25	35
Independent	17	24
University press	19	27
Association or society	10	14
Article access offered by journal (N = 71)		
Subscription-based	0	0
Hybrid open access	9	13
Gold open access	18	25
Diamond open access	42	59
Mix (Gold+Diamond)	2	3
Submission system (N = 71)		
Does not use an electronic system (manuscripts sent by email or post)	9	13
Editorial Manager	10	14
eJournalPress	0	0
Janeway	1	1
Kotahi	0	0
ESphere	0	0
OJS	22	31
Rapid Review	0	0
ScholarOne Manuscripts	12	17
Scholastica	1	1
Snapp (Springer Nature)	2	3
ARPHA (Pensoft Publishers)	1	1
Other	13	18

OJS, Open Journal System.

including such information would make it easier to find and count journals based on the type of peer review they use. Similarly, readers are often unaware of the type of peer review a given article has undergone or the changes made to the original submission due

to peer review. There have been proposals to publish 'fact labels' for each article,¹² and we have earlier advocated that changes due to peer review be displayed with each research article; however, these initiatives have not yet been widely adopted.

The present study is not without limitations. First, the study was a community project that wanted to engage additional EASE members and editors to collaborate on a small research project and the response rate was low: we were able to collect information from only 71 journals. With more than 100,000 scholarly journals in existence today, greater collaboration among publishers is needed to obtain this information on a larger scale. Second, because we did not collect participants' contact information, we were unable to explore the reasons behind the discrepancy of their answers and the information displayed on the journals' websites. Further research, including more detailed information regarding the respondents' jobs and their duration of service, might help to shed insights on this discrepancy.

Future research is also needed to determine the best way to share the data on journal peer review and to map journal practices, editorial policies, and the reasons behind these practices. Earlier independent attempts, such as the OSF Top Guidelines,¹³ the Platform for Responsible Editorial Policies,¹⁴ and even the STM NISO taxonomy¹¹ also had limited coverage of journals.

Open and transparent peer review is an emerging approach aimed at strengthening the integrity and fairness of the peer review process in academic publishing.^{15,16} To enhance the credibility of scholarly work, journals, publishers, and the broader academic community should promote open and transparent peer review practices by adopting suitable open review models, encouraging reviewer transparency, publishing peer review reports, standardizing review criteria, recognizing reviewers, facilitating post-publication review, and supporting open practices within the community. By embracing these strategies, the academic community can significantly improve the integrity and fairness of

the peer review process, ultimately benefiting the quality of scholarly communication.

In conclusion, our study has shown that the uptake of open or transparent peer review and the use of the NISO taxonomy to describe the peer review processes are still limited among journals with which members of EASE are affiliated. Further research is needed to determine barriers to, and interventions needed to promote wider adoption of, the NISO taxonomy and open and transparent peer review.

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Supplement 1: Peer review types in EASE members' journals: a survey study

Mario Malički, El Mehdi Ferrouhi, Hristina Prodanova, Seda Yilmaz Semerci, Taras Kotyk,
Siphamandla Mncube

Survey

Welcome to the Peer Review Study of EASE Member Journals

What is this research study about?

Peer review processes vary among journals. The aim of this survey is to determine the current uptake of open and transparent peer review across EASE member journals. This survey is part of the EASE [Transparency in Peer Review Project](#). Stanford IRB has determined that this research does not involve human subjects as defined in 45 CFR 46.102(e) or 21 CFR 50.3(g) as no personal information is collected. If you have any questions about the project, please contact mmalicki@stanford.edu or check our project's [website](#).

Note: Please be aware that this survey is designed using the [2023 NISO Peer Review Terminology](#), so we will be using the terms single or double **anonymized**, while indicating the previously used term – blind – in the brackets. Additionally, when filling out the survey **please describe the current (i.e., 2025) practices of your journal**; for example, while some journals might be running peer review pilot projects, we are interested in the **default/dominant approach** used by your journal. If you are affiliated with more than one journal, and willing to share information on other journals you are involved with, please send an email to mmalicki@stanford.edu, and we will forward you one or more additional survey forms.

Thank You in advance!

1. **What is the name of your journal? (mandatory)**
2. **Please insert a link to your journal's website. (mandatory)**
3. **What is your journal's ISSN (International Standard Serial Number)? (optional)**
4. **Does your journal have a peer review process defined on your website using the [2023 NISO Terminology](#)? (mandatory)**
 1. Unsure / Don't know
 2. No
 3. Yes; please provide a link to that description:
5. **Does your journal have publicly available instructions/guidelines for reviewers? (mandatory)**
 1. Unsure / Don't know
 2. No
 3. Yes; please provide a link to those guidelines:

6. **What type of peer review does your journal employ? Select multiple options if your journal offers authors to choose between various types during submission. (mandatory)**

Traditional peer review - in which review reports are NOT published alongside the article

a. Single anonymized (blind) peer review
NISO definition: Reviewer identity is not made visible to author, author identity is visible to reviewer, reviewer and author identity is visible to (decision-making) editor

b. Double anonymized (blind) peer review
NISO definition: Reviewer identity is not made visible to author, author identity is not made visible to reviewer, reviewer and author identity is visible to (decision-making) editor

c. Triple anonymized (blind) peer review
NISO definition: Reviewer identity is not made visible to author, author identity is not made visible to reviewer, reviewer and author identity is not made visible to (decision-making) editor

d. Unpublished peer review with opt-in identity reveal
Reviewers, authors, or (decision-making) editor can opt in to have their identity revealed (*Note*: this category has been adapted from the new NISO peer review taxonomy)

h. Other (please specify)

Published peer review - in which review reports ARE published alongside the article

e. open peer review
Review reports and identities of all parties are published alongside the articles (i.e., names of decision-making editor, reviewers, and authors are all made visible to each other and published alongside the article)

f. transparent peer review
Review reports are published but the identities of all parties are not published (i.e., names of decision-making editor and reviewers are not made visible nor published alongside the article)

g. published peer review with opt-in identity reveal
Review reports are published and the identities of those parties that opt-in are made visible and published (i.e., reviewer or decision-making editor can opt in to have their identity made visible or published) (*Note*: this category has been adapted from the new NISO peer review taxonomy)

7. **Please indicate the dominant practice that applies to your journal regarding editors' comments: (optional)**

- a. ALL editor(s)' comments ARE published alongside the review reports.
- b. Editor(s)' comments are NOT published.
- c. Other (please specify)

Survey Logic - For those that chose any option of published peer review (e to f from questions 7 or 8):

8. **Please indicate the dominant practice that applies to your journal regarding author responses / rebuttal letters: (optional)**

- a. ALL author responses / rebuttal letters are published.
- b. ONLY author responses / rebuttal letters of those authors that opt-in are published.
- c. Author responses / rebuttal letters are NOT published.
- d. Other (please specify)

9. **Please indicate the dominant interaction type that occurs between the editor, authors, and reviewers: (optional)**

- a. **Author(s) communicate directly only with the decision-making editor** (i.e., the author(s) do not communicate with the reviewers except through rebuttal letters that are sent to the editor)
- b. **Author(s) communicate or collaborate directly with the reviewer(s)** (i.e., authors and reviewers communicate directly before the reviewers submit their recommendation to the decision-making editor)

- c. **Reviewers communicate with one-another** (i.e., reviewers receive or comment on each other review reports before they submit their recommendation to the decision-making editor)
 - d. **Other (please specify)**
10. **How long has the journal been implementing the peer review practices you described above? (optional)**
- 1. 0 to 4 years,
 - 2. 5 to 9 years
 - 3. 10+ years
 - 4. I don't know / Not sure
11. **What year was your journal founded (i.e., started publishing manuscripts)? (optional)**
12. Please indicate if your journal allows **online comments** to articles **on your journal website** (Please note we are asking for commenting **ONLY on your journal's website** and **NOT** on third party platforms (e.g., PubPeer). Additionally, this does not refer to publication of article types such as comment / reply / letters. For example of online commenting, see [JAMA Network Open](#)):
- a. Commenting is available to anybody. Can be anonymous, require signing in and/or registration (e.g., via ORCID).
 - b. Commenting is available by invitation-only, i.e. only the editor- (or publisher-) invited/ approved individuals can comment on the journal website
 - c. Commenting is NOT possible on our journal website
 - d. Other (please specify)

We would highly appreciate if you would answer 4 more optional questions about your journal:

13. **Please indicate the main discipline of your journal** (categories adapted from [All Science Journal Classification Codes](#)) **(optional)**
- Will be designed to include major, then minor category
- a. Arts and Humanities
 - b. Health Sciences
 - c. Life Sciences
 - d. Physical Sciences
 - e. Social Sciences
 - f. Multidisciplinary Sciences
14. **Please indicate the type of Publisher for your journal: (optional)**
- 1. Institutional
 - 2. Independent
 - 3. University press
 - 4. Association/Society
 - 5. Other (please specify)
15. **Please indicate the type of article access your journal applies: (optional)**
- 1. SUBSCRIPTION-based journal - institutions, libraries, or individuals need to pay a subscription fee to articles of the journal
 - 2. HYBRID open access - authors can choose to make their article open access by paying an APC

3. GOLD open access - articles have an APC cost covered by the authors or institutions
4. DIAMOND open access - the publication of the article is free for the authors
5. Other (please specify)

16. Please indicate your journals submission system: (optional)

1. My journal does not use an electronic submission system (i.e., manuscripts are sent by email or post)
2. Editorial Manager
3. eJournalPress
4. ESphere
5. Janeway
6. Kotahi
7. Open Journal System (OJS)
8. Rapid Review
9. ScholarOne Manuscripts
10. Scholastica
11. Snapp (Springer Nature)
12. ARPHA (Pensoft Publishers)
13. Other (please specify)